

Rhythmic Stimulation of Human Brain using Embedded Neuro Soundwave

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ABSTRACT

The human brain is extremely sophisticated and remains the least understood organ in the human body. Even as we progress with great advances in fields such as aerospace science, neuroscientists still do not fully understand the human brain. Across a few thousand years of human civilisation, ancient great philosophers and modern scientists shared a common view that music therapy can help the human brain to attain desired states of relaxation, happiness and enhance brain functions. The emergence of biofeedback as a field of study in the nineteenth century opened a new frontier of research into EEG (electroencephalography) and the use of rhythmic brain entrainment with low frequencies similar to brain waves to influence and elevate the function of human brains. Traditional music therapy, binaural waves and TMS are mainstream techniques used in the mental wellness industry today. In addition, research into possible ways of producing a higher Coefficient of Efficiency was explored extensively by many researchers across the world. In 2008, Neuro Code Research Centre proposed the Neuro Soundwave technology combining music therapy with brain entrainment by directly stimulating neuronal elements with rhythmic stimulation protocols to provide therapeutic effects and brain enhancement results. Extensive research and clinical trials were conducted, methods and techniques were then reviewed and refined to produce the desired outcomes.

INTRODUCTION TO NEUROSCIENCE

Even after two hundred years of dedicated research and technological progress, neuroscientists still do not fully understand the human brain. The reason is simple - there are over 100 billion neurons in the brain, more than 10 times the current human population, and these neurons interact with each other through 1000 times as many connections.

The first written descriptions of the brain and its structure were written by Egyptians around 3700 years ago. 1200 years later, some Greek philosophers identified the brain as the organ responsible for human thoughts and feelings. In 400 B.C. Hippocrates declared "Men ought to know that from the brain, and from the brain only, arise our pleasures, joy, laughter and jests, as well as our sorrows, pains, griefs, and tears.". He was supported by Plato in the belief that the brain was responsible for our senses, intelligence and other mental processes. However others like Aristotle disagreed, believing instead that the heart was responsible. Famous European thinkers such as Galen of Bergama, Leonardo da Vinci and Rene Descartes further developed our understanding of the brain over the next 2500 years. By the early 1800s, there was no doubt that the brain was the organ responsible for perception and higher mental functions. It was during this period that scientists proposed the novel idea that the brain is separated into many regions, each dedicated to performing a specific task. This concept of brain regionalisation is an important part of modern neuroscience, although there are still some disagreements about the specific details.

Early models of brain regionalisation were not based on proper scientific evidence, and are now known to be mostly wrong. An example of this is Viennese physician Franz Joseph Gall (1758-1828). Despite lacking any concrete proof, he claimed that each of our mental faculties such as morality and intellect were controlled by separate "organs" within the brain itself. This led to the pseudoscience known as phrenology, the idea that personality and intelligence could be described by studying the lumps and bumps of a person's head.

Although phrenology has been proven false, the underlying concept of different parts of the brain performing different functions is still sound. This is a good example of the dangers of accepting popular beliefs about the brain that have not been confirmed by scientific evidence. Many people still overestimate their knowledge of how the brain works and the possible problems that might arise such as the causes and cures for various types of mental illness. The perception that these issues are simpler than they really are may have contributed to the social stigma surrounding these conditions.

Through the late 19th and early 20th centuries, scientists such as Pierre Paul Broca, Carl Wernicke, Korbinian Brodmann and Wilder Penfield presented reliable scientific proof that the brain is composed of many different areas, each specialised in a different function. By studying patients with localised brain lesions, the structural differences within the brain and the body actions produced by stimulating different brain regions, they were able to provide evidence that formed the basis for modern neuroscience.

Detailed studies of the brain's microscopic structure by Spanish scientist Santiago Ramón Y Cajal (1852-1934) led to his discovery that the nervous system is fundamentally composed of cells called neurons. For this contribution, he is considered by many to be the father of modern neuroscience. Since then, many scientists have tried to understand how these billions of neurons are organised to perform complex functions.

Brain cells are extremely diverse, with a large degree of differences in molecular structure, function, specialisation and interactions. These variations are acquired in an organised way through processes building on differences between the small numbers of cells in the early embryo. As the organism grows, interactions with already existing cells cause newly created cells to develop in specific ways, allowing very complex organs to be created in an orderly manner. Understanding brain development requires knowledge of how cells develop in response to information from outside the cell.

Since regionalisation is a crucial part of how our brains are organised, it is important to know how this regionalisation is developed. Neurons must be able to know their position in the brain before they can develop their proper functions. This concept of 'positional identity' is not just limited to neuroscience, it applies to many other cells as well. As such, many recent research efforts have focused on this area, not just in neuroscience but also for developmental biology in general.

The most commonly known model was proposed in the 1960s by Lewis Wolpert, who compared it to the French flag (a tricolor with 3 vertical stripes of blue, white, and red). In this model, a specific type of 'organiser cell' produces chemicals that diffuse outward, acting as a signal for the surrounding cells. This produces a concentration gradient which is strongest at the centre and slowly decreases as we move out. In response to this signal, cells develop into different colours. Those who receive very strong signals become blue, those which receive weaker signals become white, and those which do not receive any become red. The core concept is that through the use of cellular signals, cells can determine their position and thus respond by developing into different types of cells based on location. This concept can be expanded to include even more cell types and multiple different signals.

However, this is only a simple and basic model and we still do not know the exact details of how the brain develops regionalisation. This is an important requirement in order to develop the links between different parts of the brain in a very precise way, but still leaving room for flexibility. The process by which these links are developed is still unknown.

In 2014 February, the New York Times declared that the next frontier in science is 'inside your brain'. Although most of the brain is not fully understood, neuroscientists are gradually expanding our knowledge of how thoughts, emotions and consciousness are created within our brains.

Brain scientist Gary Marcus suggests that we are currently seeing a revolution in neuroscience. In Dec 2014, he published a compilation titled *The Future of the Brain: Essays By the World's Leading Neuroscientists*, where he wrote that "There's never been a more exciting moment in neuroscience than now". "At present, neuroscience is a collection of facts, still awaiting an overarching theory; if there has been plenty of progress, there is even more that we don't know. But a confluence of new technologies... may change that."

The study of the brain has been compared to the 'space race' of the 1960s by former President of the United States Barack Obama. He announced the BRAIN initiative, a multimillion dollar research project aimed at developing technologies to explore the brain. National Institute of Health director Francis Collins estimates that it could spend up to \$4.5 billion over the next ten years. Similar projects are also being carried out in other countries, for example the European Human Brain Project was started in 2013, and the 10-year Brain/MINDS project to map the primate brain is currently ongoing in Japan. The Chinese National People's Congress also approved the China Brain Project in March 2016. A 15-year project, it focuses on the neural basis of cognitive function, as well as improving the diagnosis and prevention of brain diseases, while also boosting information technology and artificial intelligence projects inspired by the brain. The global focus on brain research is expected to deliver many new technologies, bringing us into a new era of neuroscience.

Music Therapy for Human Brains

Many different ancient cultures shared the common belief that music can have positive effects on our mental and physical health, giving rise to the idea of music therapy. The therapeutic effect of music was usually attributed to social and cultural causes, until the scientific basis for modern medicine was established around the 1900s. Since then, the concept of music therapy has progressed from having no scientific basis to serious neuroscientific research.

According to researcher Jonathan Burdette, M.D., everyone's favourite music has a similar effect on our brains, regardless of the type of music. Any genre, whether classical, pop, rock, etc. can elicit the same response. "Music is primal. It affects all of us, but in very personal, unique ways. Your interaction with music is different from mine, but it is still powerful. Your brain has a reaction when you like or don't like something, including music. We've been able to take some baby steps into seeing that, and 'dislike' looks different than 'like' and much different than 'favourite.'"

Burdette is a neuroradiologist at Wake Forest Baptist Medical Centre and professor of radiology and vice chairman of research at Wake Forest School of Medicine. His team used fMRI (functional magnetic resonance imaging) to map the brain activity of 21 subjects by studying changes in blood flow. Brain scans were made while they listened to music they liked and disliked from 5 genres (classical, country, rap, rock, Chinese opera) as well as their personal favourite song.

The fMRI scans produced a consistent result where the effect on brain connectivity depended on the subject's preference rather than the type of music they listened to. The greatest impact was on the default mode network, a brain circuit known to participate in internally focused thought, empathy and self-awareness. This circuit was poorly connected when listening to music they disliked, however the connection improved when listening to music they liked, and the best results were shown when listening to their favourites. Listening to favourite songs also improved the connectivity between the brain area specialised in hearing and brain regions responsible for memory and social emotion.

"Given that music preferences are uniquely individualized phenomena and that music can vary in acoustic complexity and the presence or absence of lyrics, the consistency of our results was unexpected," the researchers wrote in the journal *Nature Scientific Reports* (Aug. 28, 2014). "These findings may explain why comparable emotional and mental states can be experienced by people listening to music that differs as widely as Beethoven and Eminem." Burdette was not surprised by the effect on the connectivity seen in the participants' brains when they were listening to their favourite tunes. "There are probably some features in music that make you feel a certain way, but it's your experience with it that is even more important. Your associations with certain music involve many different parts of the brain, and they're very strong. In some cases, you might not even like the particular song, but you like the memories or feelings that you associate with it."

Other projects run by Burdette and his colleagues at the School of Medicine and the University of North Carolina-Greensboro have shown that trained musicians are better than the average person at tasks requiring a combination of both sight and hearing. They also found that activity in brain regions specialised in vision decreases when focusing on listening, and different degrees of musical complexity have different effects on functional brain connectivity. "I find this type of work fascinating, because I think music is so important," Burdette said. "If science can help get more people to recognize what music does to and for us, great."

Burdette's research involves much more than just music, for example his most recent work provides evidence that brain volume can accurately predict whether or not attempts by elderly to lose weight will be successful. But for him, music has always played a role in his life - he can play the viola, piano and guitar, and learned how to sing since he was a child. Even now, he participates in the chorus of the Piedmont Opera where he has been a board member for over a decade. He even has some experience as a conductor. His wife, Shona Simpson, plays the piano, and their three teenage daughters - Fiona, Ellie and Jessie - perform professionally as the Dan River Girls. His brother, Kevin, is a singer who has appeared as a soloist with the Metropolitan Opera, Los Angeles Philharmonic and other top-tier opera companies and symphony orchestras. "Music is my avocation, Radiology is my vocation.", says Burdette. He is also deeply interested, if not directly involved, in music's clinical applications. "Music isn't going to cure anything, but it definitely can play a therapeutic role," he said.

Burdette points out that in countries such as Germany, music therapy is widely used as a vital part of the rehabilitation process for people who have had strokes, brain surgery or traumatic brain injuries. "If you're trying to restore neuroplasticity in the brain, to re-establish some of the connections that were there before the injury, music can be a big help, and I'd like to see it used more widely in this country," he said. Burdette also is a proponent of programs that help people with Alzheimer's, dementia and other cognitive and physical problems re-connect with the world through

music. One such program is Music & Memory, which employs iPods with customized playlists featuring songs popular when the participating individual was under 30 years old. "You can actually see the power of music," Burdette said. "People who were just sitting there, not engaged in anything, light up when they start hearing music from when they were 25. "It's fantastic. What else can do that? I can't think of anything other than music."

A STEP BEYOND MUSIC THERAPY

In 1990, American psychologist and biofeedback pioneer Thomas Budzynski published a research paper where low frequency waves (0.5Hz to 30Hz) were shown to reliably affect behaviour and mental state. When brainwaves are measured on the surface of the scalp, they can be categorised based on their frequency and amplitudes. These categories correspond to specific states of excitement or cortical arousal, in other words it is possible to detect a person's mental state by studying their brainwaves. For example, we would expect to see a beta EEG pattern when looking at an alert and very focused person. The amplitude would be relatively small (<10uV) with frequency around 14-30Hz. When going down to an alert but relaxed state, bursts of alpha frequencies (8-13Hz) up to 150uV amplitude can be seen. Further transition into slight drowsiness causes theta waves to appear, with frequencies of 4-7Hz and amplitude of 5-20uV.

Researchers have categorised the state dominated by theta waves as Stage 1 sleep. Sinking deeper into Stage 2 sleep produces short bursts of high frequency, large amplitude waves called sleep spindles. Stages 3 and 4 show characteristic delta waves with low frequencies (0.5-3Hz) and varying amplitude up to ~200uV.

An important characteristic of these bands is that they usually do not appear by themselves. Most of the time there will be a dominant frequency mixed with others. For example, some people will display a primarily alpha pattern, together with occasional beta and theta patterns. Furthermore, a theta pattern is associated with drowsiness, but if the person becomes more alert this will be interrupted by bursts of alpha patterns, on the other hand if the person becomes sleepier delta patterns will begin to appear. The transition into theta state without alpha and beta patterns usually indicates unconsciousness in most people. An EEG reading showing primary theta patterns with some alpha and beta usually results in mixed feelings of drowsiness and consciousness, similar to the mental state achieved by meditation.

In 1991, it was shown that beta frequency soundwaves at 18-21Hz seemed to improve cognitive function in ADHD(Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder) children. This evidence was presented by Harold Russell, Ph.D. at the AAPB (Association of Applied Psychophysiology and Biofeedback) Annual Meeting in Dallas, Texas. EEG readings of ADHD children display higher than average theta patterns and lower than normal beta patterns. Dr. Russell also cites the Dr. Marion Diamond's book "Enhancing Heredity" (1988), which showed that sensory stimulation of rat brains increased the growth of dendrites. These changes are possible at any age in any animal.

Together with his colleague John Carter, Russell found that sound wave stimulation of cortical hemispheres could significantly improve the performance of students. Each hemisphere of the brain specialises in different tasks, and stimulation of the weaker hemisphere was shown to improve its function. Test subjects were selected from students with a greater than 10 point difference in the Verbal and Performance score on the WAIS IQ test. Students with lower Verbal scores were exposed to beta frequencies targeted at the left hemisphere, students with lower Performance scores received soundwaves in the right hemisphere, and all children were also given a relaxation audiotape to be used at home each night. After 30-40 minute training sessions, these students displayed a significant improvement in their scores on the respective sections. However, attempts to train the higher performing hemisphere produced no improvements. Russell also suggests that ADHD children can be taught to control their brainwave state by combining sound wave stimulation with EEG biofeedback training.

In a PhD dissertation, Foster (1990) presented reliable data and references showing that sound waves alone are sufficient to produce EEG entrainment.

When manipulating alpha EEG, Foster specifically distinguishes between the use of biofeedback and binaural beats. Foster states: "Alpha brain wave biofeedback is considered a consciousness self-regulation technique while alpha frequency binaural beats stimulation is considered a consciousness management technique.", and "both techniques could be considered to contain components of both self-regulation and management of consciousness."

A significant amount of research and documentation already exists regarding binaural beats (refer to Oster, 1973), however Foster noted that consciousness management via the use of binaural beat stimulation has only received the attention of a small minority of researchers (Atwater, 1988).

A binaural beat is created by outputting two different frequencies, one into each ear. As a result, a third tone can be heard, which is based on the difference in frequency of the other two tones. For example, a 200Hz tone in one ear and a 210Hz tone in the other produces a 10Hz "beat" tone. According to Foster, this is produced by "...an auditory brainstem response which originates in the superior olivary nucleus of each hemisphere. The beat results from the interaction of two afferent auditory impulses, originating in opposite ears, below 1000 Hz; and which differ in frequency between one and 30 Hz." As the two waveforms flow in and out of phase within the superior olivary nuclei, the result is a different third tone.

Oster (1973) states that binaural beats were first known to be used in 1839, originally by German scientist H.W. Dove. Binaural beats are now used by manufacturers of audiotapes to produce certain mental states in listeners, especially relaxation. As part of his study, Foster studied the extent to which binaural beats at an alpha frequency could produce an increase in alpha. While the binaural beats did result in higher levels of alpha, a control group subjected to artificially produced wave sounds also showed a similar increase in alpha. Subjects seemed to produce larger increases in alpha when concentrating on the binaural beat.

BRAIN STIMULATION USING NEURO SOUNDWAVES

Recently, there has been increased focus on the idea of direct rhythmical stimulation of neurons within the brain. The ability to reliably induce and control brain oscillations in a functionally meaningful way would be a breakthrough in the study and therapeutic use of brain oscillations. It is possible to perform a controlled intervention into human brain oscillations in a non-invasive manner by using low frequency waves embedded into music, thus combining the benefits of music Therapy and Brain Oscillation to provide brain stimulation with therapeutic effects. This technique developed by Neuro Code Research is termed Neuro Soundwave Technique.

In our research, we focus on one such type of intervention, the direct entrainment of brain oscillations by a specifically generated soundwave with controlled waveform, frequencies and amplitudes. Behaviourally, such entrainment seems to alter specific aspects of perception depending on the frequency of stimulation, informing models on the functional role of oscillatory activity. This indicates that human brain oscillations and function may be promoted in a controlled way by focal entrainment, with great potential for probing into brain oscillations and their causal role.

Physiological rhythms are common in all living organisms. In the brain, oscillations are supported by distinct neuronal elements across different spatial scales. These elements range from the single neuron over neuronal circuits to thalamo-cortical and cortico-cortical networks at the macroscopic level. Furthermore, brain oscillations occur in distinct frequency bands as a function of micro- and macro-network architecture. Some aspects of brain activity can therefore be described in a simplified model as a system of hierarchically stacked neuronal oscillators, that cycle and interact at different frequencies.

One of the computational processes that oscillations likely enable is the dynamic routing/gating of information through the synchronization of neuronal elements. From such a network perspective, lower frequency oscillations in the theta to alpha bands (4–12 Hz) have been related to long-distance, area-to-area interactions, and higher frequency gamma-oscillations (20–100 Hz) to local neuronal communication, coordinated in a multi-band neuronal workspace through cross-frequency interactions. Perception also relies on processes that enable effective selection and integration of relevant information from the vast amount of sensory inputs that is constantly bombarding our brain. In support of the hypothesis that differences in frequencies across structures may provide important clues to these functions, posterior gamma-oscillations (30–100 Hz, of likely intracortical origin) have been assigned roles in feature binding, and posterior alpha-band oscillations (8–14 Hz, of thalamo-cortical origin) in input regulation, and attentional selection.

One property of oscillating elements commonly found in nature is that they are self-sustained and dynamic. However, it is possible to induce perturbations with an external force, and if this force is periodic the natural oscillation may then become synchronized to the periodic event. Synchronization here means that the oscillating element starts to cycle with the same period as the external force. Or in other terms, the oscillator becomes entrained or locked to the external event. In this context, synchronization, entrainment, and locking are synonymous. We will use the term entrainment to denote synchronization to a rhythmic stream (or train) of external events.

With a sound understanding of the functional aspects of the brain and the frequencies that could produce effective oscillations, we began to generate and synthesize the desired waveforms that are useful to the human brains. Research direction takes 2 different paths. The first direction is to develop an effective soundwave that could assist in human brain development - with a particular focus on enhancing attention and focus, improving memory and

enhancing sensory perception of environmental scenery and objects. The second research direction is the development of effective soundwaves that could induce sleepiness, relaxation and positive emotions.

APPROACH TO DEVELOPMENT OF NEURO SOUNDWAVE FOR RELAXATION AND SLEEP

At the root of all our thoughts, emotions and behaviours is the communication between neurons within our brains. Brainwaves are produced by synchronised electrical pulses from masses of neurons communicating with each other, which can then be detected using sensors placed on the scalp. They are divided into bandwidths to describe their functions, but are best thought of as a continuous spectrum of consciousness; from slow, loud and functional - to fast, subtle, and complex.

It is a handy analogy to think of brainwaves as musical notes - the low frequency waves are like a deeply penetrating drum beat, while the higher frequency brainwaves are more like a subtle high pitched flute. Like a symphony, the higher and lower frequencies link and cohere with each other through harmonics. Our brainwaves change according to what we are doing and feeling. When slower brainwaves are dominant we feel tired, slow, sluggish, or dreamy. The higher frequencies are dominant when we feel wired, or hyper-alert. The descriptions that follow are only broad descriptions - in practice things are far more complex, and brainwaves reflect different aspects when they occur in different locations in the brain.

Brainwave speed is measured in Hertz (cycles per second) and they are divided into bands delineating slow, moderate, and fast waves. They are broadly classified into 5 types of brain waves as illustrated in the chart below:

Beta brainwaves (12-25Hz) dominate our normal waking state of consciousness when attention is directed towards cognitive tasks and the outside world. Beta is a 'fast' activity, present when we are alert, attentive, engaged in problem solving, judgment, decision making, or focused mental activity.

Alpha brainwaves (8-12Hz) are dominant during quietly flowing thoughts, and in some meditative states. Alpha is 'the power of now', being here, in the present. Alpha is the resting state for the brain. Alpha waves aid overall mental coordination, calmness, alertness, mind/body integration and learning.

Theta brainwaves (4-8Hz) occur most often in sleep but are also dominant in deep meditation. Theta is our gateway to learning, memory, and intuition. In theta, our senses are withdrawn from the external world and focused on signals originating from within. It is that twilight state which we normally only experience fleetingly as we wake or drift off to sleep. In theta we are in a dream; vivid imagery, intuition and information beyond our normal conscious awareness. It's where we hold our 'stuff', our fears, troubled history, and nightmares.

Delta brainwaves (0.5-4Hz) are slow, loud brainwaves (low frequency and deeply penetrating, like a drum beat). They are generated in deepest meditation and dreamless sleep. Delta waves suspend external awareness and are the source of empathy. Healing and regeneration are stimulated in this state, and that is why deep restorative sleep is so essential to the healing process.

Gamma brainwaves (>25Hz) are the fastest of brain waves (high frequency, like a flute), and relate to simultaneous processing of information from different brain areas. Gamma brainwaves pass information rapidly and quietly. The most subtle of the brainwave frequencies, the mind has to be quiet to access gamma.

Our brainwave profile and our daily experience of the world are inseparable. When our brainwaves are out of balance, there will be corresponding problems in our emotional or neuro-physical health. Research has identified brainwave patterns associated with all sorts of emotional and neurological conditions.

Over-arousal in certain brain areas is linked with anxiety disorders, sleep problems, nightmares, hyper-vigilance, impulsive behaviour, anger/aggression, agitated depression, chronic nerve pain and spasticity. Under-arousal in certain brain areas leads to some types of depression, attention deficit, chronic pain and insomnia. A combination of under-arousal and over-arousal is seen in cases of anxiety, depression and ADHD. Instabilities in brain rhythms correlate with tics, obsessive-compulsive disorder, aggressive behaviour, rage, bruxism, panic attacks, bipolar disorder, migraines, narcolepsy, epilepsy, sleep apnea, vertigo, tinnitus, anorexia/bulimia, PMT, diabetes, hypoglycaemia and explosive behaviour.

Brain wave patterns could be modified by chemical interventions such as medications or recreational drugs as the most common methods to alter brain function. Other alternative methods have been proposed and tested over the years. More established research encompasses the fields of brain entrainment, music therapy and Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS).

The approach adopted by Neuro Code provides a method for development of mental wellness enhancement waves combining music therapy and brain entrainment through low frequency waves.

The illustration below shows the components of Neuro Soundwave and its typical applications.

The method of making music embedded with frequencies similar to brain wave frequencies that is conducive to sleep includes the following steps in sequence:

- (1) To generate a sine wave with frequencies starting from the β (Beta) wave frequency (12-30 Hz) and decrease gradually to the frequency of the δ (Delta) wave at (0.5-4 Hz). As the frequency reduces, the amplitude decreases accordingly.

- (2) The sine wave selected in step (1) is decomposed into N harmonics by Fast Fourier Transformation algorithm, where $N > 5$.

Any waveform can be decomposed into an infinite series of sine waves added together. This is called Fourier transform.

- (3) Select M harmonics from N harmonics and integrate these M harmonics into one sound wave by using a fixed waveform generator, where $M > 2$.
- (4) Select the music, preferably suitable for relaxing music.

- (5) Through the music synthesizer and using the FM music synthesis method, the integrated sound wave and the synchronized music are superposed and synthesized. The result is a music embedded with Neuro Soundwave that helps sleep.

Several experiments were carried out to explore and identify effective Neuro Soundwaves.

Example one:

- (1) To generate a sine wave with frequencies starting from 25Hz and decrease gradually by 2Hz/5mins interval to 0.5Hz.
- (2) The sine wave selected in step (1) is decomposed into 50 harmonics by Fast Fourier Transformation algorithm.
- (3) Select 5 harmonics from 50 harmonics and integrate these 5 harmonics into one sound wave by using a fixed waveform generator.
- (4) Select the music, preferably suitable for relaxing music.
- (5) Through the music synthesizer and using the FM music synthesis method, the integrated sound wave and the synchronized music are superposed and synthesized. Composes music that helps sleep.

Example two:

- (1) To generate a sine wave with frequencies starting from 25Hz and decrease gradually by 1Hz/5mins interval to 1Hz.
- (2) The sine wave selected in step (1) is decomposed into 30 harmonics by Fast Fourier Transformation algorithm.
- (3) Select 6 harmonics from 30 harmonics and integrate these 6 harmonics into one sound wave by using a fixed waveform generator.
- (4) Select the music, preferably suitable for relaxing music.
- (5) Through the music synthesizer and using the FM music synthesis method, the integrated sound wave and the synchronized music are superposed and synthesized. Composes music that helps sleep.

Example three:

- (1) To generate a sine wave with frequencies starting from 20Hz and decrease gradually by 3Hz/5mins interval to 3Hz.
- (2) The sine wave selected in step (1) is decomposed into 40 harmonics by Fast Fourier Transformation algorithm.
- (3) Select 4 harmonics from 40 harmonics and integrate these 4 harmonics into one sound wave by using a fixed waveform generator.
- (4) Select the music, preferably suitable for relaxing music.
- (5) Through the music synthesizer and using the FM music synthesis method, the integrated sound wave and the synchronized music are superposed and synthesized. Composes music that helps sleep.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

Extensive research was carried out by Neuro Code Research Centre to establish the effectiveness of new techniques in brain development and mental wellness enhancement. Combining music therapy and brain entrainment using brain wave frequencies, it was found that subjects under clinical trials could attain soothing states of relaxation leading to good quality sleep. The technique uses mathematical computation of the Fast Fourier Transform to extract harmonics from a pre-developed waveform. By combining desired harmonics with music, the resulting Neuro Soundwave was proven to be a breakthrough technology in brain development and mental wellness enhancement. Two PCT patents were filed in 2017, and this invention could trigger further development in the area of music therapy and brain oscillation techniques to provide viable and stable solutions for the biofeedback industry.

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